

Study of Clinical Profile and Treatment Outcome of Acute Burn Patients**Kundan Kumar¹, Mithilesh Kumar², Sushant Kumar Sharma³**¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar³Professor, Department of General Surgery, Sri Krishna Medical College and Hospital, Muzaffarpur, Bihar

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Abstract:

Background: Burn injuries pose a serious health risk due to their high rate of morbidity, disability, and mortality among young and middle-aged individuals. There are societal issues related to burn damage as well. It might be associated with unintentional, suicidal, or homicidal reasons. In India, there is a dearth of study on burn injuries despite their significance from a clinical and societal standpoint. In order to determine the causes of burns, their clinical characteristics, and the outcomes of burn patients' treatment at our institute, we thus attempted to draw attention to our findings in this study.

Methods: From February to July of 2024, patients with burn injuries hospitalized to the surgery wards and burn ICU of SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, participated in this observational study. We have examined 226 burn patients who were admitted to our institute's burn unit and general surgery units. Both sexes and burn patients older than 18 were included in the study.

Results: 226 patients in all suffered burn injuries. 162 male and 64 female made up the M:F ratio of 2.53:1. The majority of affected males (71.68%) were compared to females. In this study, the majority of burn patients were between the ages of 21 and 30. that is, 42.02%. Patients in the 50–75 age range were less numerous. Regarding the causes, the greatest number of patients are observed during household activities, with electricity accounting for the second-highest number of cases (26.99%). Suicidal thoughts account for a smaller percentage of patients (3.53), and seven instances have an unclear etiology.

Conclusion: Preventing burn injuries is extremely difficult, but it is necessary to reduce the high morbidity and mortality that follow a burn injury. We must take all necessary steps to reduce its occurrence. There is only so much that social workers, physicians, paramedics, and administrators can do to reduce the number of burn injuries that occur in India.

Keywords: preventive measures, incidence, causes, types of burn, house hold activities.

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Introduction

Burn injuries are extremely significant, affecting a patient's quality of life and emotional health. According to estimates from the World Health Organization, burn injuries from fires claim the lives of over 300,000 people each year worldwide. [1] Burn injuries brought on by fire, flames, smoke, hot materials, electric current, lightning, and contact with corrosive substances have also been categorized by the World Health Organization (WHO). [2]

The burden of sickness in the world is still greatly increased by burn injuries. They are responsible for more than 310,000 unintentional fire-related deaths annually, the most of which occur in youth and young adults. The World Health Organization reports that the incidence rate in low- and middle-

income nations is 1.3, while in high-income nations it is 0.14 per 100,000 people. More than 95% of burn injuries that result in death happen in developing nations. [6]

According to recent studies on injuries, 40% of unintended home-related injuries across all age groups are burns, making them one of the main causes of injuries. Women have been documented to have sustained a high percentage of these burn injuries. [4] A person's lifetime risk of having burns is estimated to be 1%. [5] After taking into account each of these variables, a study was carried out with the aim of examining the sociodemographic characteristics of burn patients in the northern part of India, as well as the causes and consequences of

burn injuries in patients who are admitted to our institution.

Materials and Methods

Between February and July of 2024, patients with burn injuries admitted to the general surgical wards and burn ICU of Sri Krishna Medical College & Hospital in Muzaffarpur, Bihar, participated in this observational study.

We have attempted to highlight the significance of burn injury prevalence and its many forms in this study. risk factors, modes of occurrence, and identifying preventive strategies. 226 patients with burns who were admitted to our institute's general surgical units have been the subject of our study. Both sexes and burn patients older than 18 were included in the study. Name, age, sex, place of occurrence, and injury-related information, such as the etiology of burn injuries, the area of the burn, the injured anatomic locations, and inhalation injury, were all recorded in the information

gathered. Burn injuries can be caused by flame, scald, contact, or electrical burns.

All patients received either Ringer's lactate or normal saline for initial resuscitation. Silver sulphadiazine was used topically until healing through re-epithelialization took place. Before the skin was grafted, the majority of wounds on the trunk and extremities were treated until the eschar separated.

Results

226 study participants in all suffered burn injuries. Of the 226 individuals, 162 were male and 64 were female, with a M: F ratio of 2.53 to 1. Comparatively speaking, males were impacted 71.68% more frequently than females. 42.02% of the burn patients were between the ages of 21 and 30. The age group of 51 to 60 years old had the lowest percentage of burn patients, at 4.47%. In Table 1, this distribution is displayed.

Table 1: Distribution of cases with their age group in years

Age group (in yrs.)	Male	Percentage	Female	Percentage	Total	Percentage
< 20	26	11.50%	13	5.75%	39	17.25%
21-30	75	33.18%	20	8.84%	95	42.02%
31-40	29	12.83%	12	5.30%	41	18.13%
41-50	18	7.96%	9	3.98%	27	11.94%
51-60	7	3.09%	3	1.38%	10	4.47%
> 60	7	3.09%	7	3.09%	14	6.18%
All	162	71.68%	64	28.31%	226	100%

Maximum patients have (81) 25-50% age of burns as per table 2. Least patients are seen in 50-75 percentage of burn.

Table 2: Distribution of cases with percentage of burn

Percentage of burn	Number of patients	Percentage
< 25%	80	35.39%
25-50%	81	35.84%
50-75%	31	13.71%
> 75%	34	15.04%
Total	226	100%

A lot of accidents occurred at home and in the kitchen. Pump stoves (Kerosene) are used commonly for cooking purposes. The mechanisms most commonly found in these injuries were due to explosion of stoves after excessive pumping, filling of fuel while the stove was on. Gas cylinder related injuries occurred in houses and at work places.

Table 3: Distribution of case with their causes

Causes	Number	Percentage
House hold activities	121	53.53%
Electric current	61	26.99%
Work place	16	7.07%
Suicidal	8	3.53%
Hot liquid	13	5.75%
unknown	7	3.09%
Total	226	100%

As per table no.3, maximum burns are due to activities at home seen in 53.53%. Electricity is causing second highest cases (26.99%), less number of patients are suicidal (3.53) and unknown etiology seen in seven patients. These type of accidents occurred when someone forgot to switch

off the cylinder valve, use of damaged pipe leading to leakage and the explosion following lighting in a closed kitchen. Oil lamps ('kupi'), candles and hurricane-lanterns, diyas (Clay baked earthen oil lamps) were also responsible to number of burns. All accidents were happened due to human

mistake. Irrespective of fuel/burners, both flame burns and scald occurred in kitchen.

Discussion

In low- and middle-income nations, burn injuries continue to be one of the most common causes of mortality and morbidity despite the significant advancements in medical technology. Additionally, burn injuries have a lasting societal impact. A burn is a form of injury that happens in different layers of skin cells and can be caused by flames or contact burns from hot liquids, according to the International Society for Burn Injuries (ISBI). Burn injuries can include those induced by chemicals or electricity on the skin, UV rays, radioactivity, and smoke inhalation injuries that cause lung impairment.[6]

More than 90% of burns can be avoided, yet they nevertheless pose a serious threat to public health.[7] distinct communities and social groups have dramatically distinct burn injury etiologies and characteristics. However, injuries may result from homicidal, suicidal, or unintentional acts. The effects of burns range from superficial burns and scalds to internal organ damage, depending on the depth and severity of the burns as well as the accessibility and availability of medical care. The age group of 21 to 30 years old accounted for the largest percentage of patients (42.02%), suggesting that this age group was exposed to burn agents at a higher rate than any other. These outcomes agree with the findings of the other earlier research.[8,9]

The study done by Attia AF et al. and Singh MV et al. shows that; about 66% of the patients were in the age group of 21-50 years and is the most productive age group in our country and more susceptible to injuries both in home and in workplace. This type of age distribution is similar to other studies in India and outside.[10,11] Although of prevention of burns has increased now, but still many people suffered burn injuries yearly.[9] Severe burns can lead to extremely serious deformity, disability, or even death.[12] Almost 80% of the patients were between 18 and 40 years old, which is similar to other studies.[13,14] Now study, 59% of the burn injury admissions were males, showing a peak between 21 to 30 years (33.18%), followed by 31 to 40 years (12.83%). In contrast, Ahuja and Bhattacharya (2002) reported higher admissions of women with burns (58%).[13] Gender differences play a significant role in the risk of burn injuries, across a spectrum with a predominance of women injured in fires from cooking and heating fuels in the developing world. Moreover in the developing country like India, females are married earlier than males in the family and are more exposed to social and family stress. In this study 35.84% patients sustained major burns injuries involving 25-50% of

body surface areas and 28.75% of patients have involvement of more than fifty percent of surface areas, which is consistent with other studies.[15,16] Kumar (2000) observed that among those with burn injuries, 37% had an involvement of >20% of the body surface area.[17] In our study, 53.53% patients were suffering from burns by activities in house hold, 26.99% were suffering from electric current injury 7.07% of patients were from burns at work place like factory workers welding shops using LPG cylinders and only 3.09% were suffering from burns of unknown aetiology-some patients have history of psychiatric illness. In a study done by Gupta A et al, 72% patients got thermal burns, 7% got scalds and 17% got electric burns.[18] Also study conducted by Nnabuko REE et al reported that the most frequently affected age group was in the second decade of life (33.3%). Contact with live wire or contact with an object that was in contact with a live wire (secondary contact) accounted for 43 of 84 cases (51%). Home was the most common location where injury occurred (51.2%). [19]

Patients with severe burns often need long-term hospitalization and undergo multiple surgical procedures, and some require readmission for reconstructive surgery. The impact of physical disfigurement and pain due to severe burns are far-reaching, and the psychological impairments can last a lifetime. [20] In developing nations, burn continues to be endemic because of large scale use of unsafe stoves and fuel. Majority of burns were caused by flame, with kerosene. This is probably due to its availability and common use as domestic fuels. In relation to causes of burn most of patients had accidental burns while 3.53% sustained suicidal and 5.75% had burns by hot liquid. burns. Our observations conform to published reports.

Some females do not reveal the true cause of burn but instead blame it on some accidental reason as cause of their burns. It may be due to pressure of relatives and because of anxiety, patients initially confess to have sustained accidental burns. However, these medicolegal aspects are beyond the scope of the present study. In the present study it was observed that the majority of burns admitted to hospital occurred at home. These observations are consistent with those reported by others.[9,17] The problems of burn injuries is more severe developing countries, due to the reason that burn patients requires more specialized units are expensive and they are not always available.[20] Public awareness through different communication medias and education through schools colleges could be provided about burn-related safety measures. Good awareness on safer first-aid practices such as applying cold water soon after sustaining burns is essential. Precautions and safety measures taken during food preparation care of

electricity wires and in the working places like factories welding shops could help to prevent burns. There should be availability of Up To Date burn care centers in all public institutions as near to the place of accident as possible.

Conclusion

Following an accident, there is a need for particular recommendations to minimize pain and prevent major morbidity and mortality. These recommendations stem from an analysis of the epidemiological characteristics of burns. Stronger national initiatives should be developed to protect the impoverished and promote health. To reduce the occurrence of burns, government authorities, medical professionals, and well-trained social workers should collaborate. It is necessary to create sustainable, culturally appropriate, and reasonably priced therapies for patients suffering from burn injuries as well as for their prevention and management. Interventions include educating the public, developing burn programs, enforcing them strictly, and providing the newest facilities for emergency burn care.

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